

#EduTok: A qualitative content analysis of grammar-related *TikTok* videos as nano-learning tools

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This study illustrates how EduTok applies Nano-Learning principles to improve grammar instruction, offering avenues for targeted, efficient language learning. Nano-Learning (NL) is gaining traction in modern education due to its focused, adaptive content presentation. EduTok videos are utilized to teach topics like English grammar, presenting information in manageable segments. This study analyzed 55 videos from one *TikTok* account, focused on video length, content, and NL principles. The findings showed that EduTok videos focus on a single grammatical concept, real-world application in everyday life, and common grammatical mistakes, using multimodal elements for contextual learning. The key features of these nano-learning videos include brevity, video length, visual engagement, and interactive delivery. The instructional style includes grammar tips, binary exercises, and conversational approaches to encourage learner engagement and accessibility.

Keywords: Content Analysis; EduTok; Grammar Learning; Nano-Learning; *TikTok*

1. Introduction

The integration of technology has become a preeminent global trend in different education systems. It serves as an input, a means of delivery, a skill, a tool for planning, and a provider of social and cultural contexts (UNESCO, 2024). This composite role makes technology an essential instrument for bridging diverse learning situations and addressing pedagogical challenges (Cadiz et al., 2024; Kimmons et al., 2020) in the 21st century educational landscape.

Since the pandemic, people have become more proactive and flexible in finding new resources due to imposed restrictions and limited options. Online platforms, particularly social networking sites, have gained popularity for

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educational purposes, especially among students who frequently exchange knowledge through these applications via peer discussions, shared resources, and tutorials. Kumar & Nanda (2022) revealed in their study that many opportunities have emerged in this global network for developing interactive learning strategies that meet the diverse and evolving needs of learners. They further explain that these opportunities are being explored across both formal (institutionalized) and informal (self-directed) learning contexts.

EduTok videos are among the media outputs that exemplify the characteristics of a new resource. 'EduTok' is a portmanteau of 'education' and 'TikTok,' launched as an initiative by the social media application *TikTok*. Since 2019, content creators have used #EduTok to create and share educational content (i.e., short-form videos) on their platforms. This started as an online challenge encouraging app users to develop significant educational videos. EduTok seeks to democratize learning by developing educational materials that are free, accessible, and usable for a broader audience (Salazar-Vallejo & Rivera-Rogel, 2023). It also aims to dismantle barriers to quality education using technology and other innovative methods.

Nano-learning principles are commonly applied in EduTok videos. Nano-learning, as referred to by Pham et al. (2023, p. 212), is a "learning strategy that delivers content in small, easily digestible chunks that can be understood in a short amount of time." This allows viewers and learners to comprehend and break down information in small, specific ways. It also acknowledges how information is communicated in a fast-paced manner, particularly in light of today's 47-second attention span among students, which is continually decreasing (Mark, cited in Oaten, 2024). Information retention can be significantly enhanced using visually engaging materials, concise content delivery, and interactive elements. The decreasing attention span involves innovative approaches and methods to help learners focus on key points without feeling overwhelmed. This adaptation aligns with the ever-evolving needs of learners in the digital age while maintaining content quality.

Based on the contextualization present in the current learning situation, this article primarily aims to analyze EduTok videos focused on teaching and learning English grammar. The analysis is guided by the following research questions:

- (1) What grammar topics and competencies are evident in the EduTok videos surveyed?
- (2) What key observations and insights can be drawn from the content of the videos?
- (3) How are nano-learning characteristics integrated in the EduTok videos?

2. Background

Integrating diverse materials is now becoming more apparent in second-language teaching and learning. There are various language learning applications (e.g., *Duolingo*, *Babbel*, *Rosetta Stone*, etc.) and gamified learning platforms (e.g., *Memrise*, *Lingvist*, etc.) that use games, and immersive and interactive activities to train learners in different language competencies. Virtual reality and augmented reality tools (e.g., *Google Expeditions*, *Mondly VR*, etc.) are now integrated to provide additional learning experiences. Various language exchange platforms (e.g., *HelloTalk*, *Tandem*, etc.) also help learners experience actual interaction with native speakers. Furthermore, the prominence of artificial intelligence tools (e.g., *ChatGPT*, *Microsoft Copilot*, *Google Gemini*, etc.) provides a supplement or alternative to the conventional structure and form of second language learning. However, despite the number of platforms, only a few focus on a single, specific grammar competency (Abutalebi & Clahsen, 2022; Zainuddin & Yunus, 2022). When available, notable limitations include the absence of cultural context in language use (Xia et al., 2024). Additionally, these factors have led to standardized discussions that fail to: (a) accommodate individual learning styles; (b) provide sufficient comprehensive resources; (c) address access issues; (d) ensure content quality; and (e) support language skills retention.

Although *TikTok* is not initially considered an educational platform, as it was designed for short-form video sharing on entertaining content (e.g., dance challenges, comedy skits, and music dubbing), it has become increasingly popular for educational content creation. The platform now offers tutorials, explanations, and lessons on various topics, including language learning, transforming it into a suitable tool for educational purposes (Bouchard, 2024). Several studies highlight the significant impact of *TikTok* as a platform for improving language skills. Cagas (2022) found that learning speaking skills through *TikTok* fosters a positive learning environment and boosts students' confidence in English. Revesencio et al. (2022) emphasized how *TikTok* helps students learn new English words, while Ananda and Komara (2024) found that students' habits of watching *TikTok* content in English are positively linked to their grammar performance. Together, these studies suggest that *TikTok* can be a valuable resource for improving various aspects of language learning, including grammar.

Accessing EduTok videos, specifically those about language learning, becomes part of their 'everyday scroll' by simply: (a) watching the linguistic information (e.g., sounds, phrases, linguistic and cultural nuances) that the content creators post, stitching the videos and posting them; and (b) practicing their writing and comprehension skills through comments, which can also receive feedback.

Over the years, consumption of social media content on platforms such as *TikTok* has been on the rise due to its short video format and engaging nature. Nano-learning is defined as a highly targeted approach of breaking complex subjects into small and manageable chunks to present a short, straightforward idea interestingly (Mariappan, 2024). With the increasing popularity of *TikTok* as a nano-learning platform, more research has been carried out to understand its potential and effectiveness in language learning and education. The study by Mariappan (2024) revealed that teachers can utilize *TikTok* to create bite-sized lessons and incorporate visual demonstrations, interactive challenges, and relevant content to teach grammar concepts.

The study conducted by Khlaif and Salha (2024) suggests that *TikTok* can be utilized to create and facilitate high-quality e-learning resources that can benefit the needs of the new generation of learners. They further highlighted that this can be attributed to the ability of *TikTok* to deliver targeted, bite-sized content in less than 60 seconds. Apart from this, they also identified some of the key features of nano-learning which include self-contained, small, and unified content focused on a single concept or objective and short pieces of audio, video, and graphical content. Based on these principles, the brevity of nano-learning content can address the need for methods and tools that do not cognitively overload students (Chamorro-Atalaya et al., 2024).

Nano-learning briefly refers to condensing contents into smaller, bite-sized learning capsules. As mentioned by Garcia et al. (2022, p. 3), “nano-learning is about providing digestible small learning units, ideally where and when students need them.” This supports the argument of Bahodir (2021), in which he highlighted the need to present learning materials in concise portions because this allows for easier processing of information and makes the learner more productive, attentive, and able to retain more.

Apart from its brevity, nano-learning is highly targeted, easily accessible, and can be delivered through multimedia (Moser, 2024). Visual elements such as images, graphics, animations, videos, and other visual representations of information are core components in creating interactive multimedia content. The ability of nano-learning to integrate multiple forms of media—text, visual, audio, video, and interactivity—within a single learning experience not only attracts a variety of learners but also allows the creation of more engaging content. Furthermore, the findings of the study by Khlaif and Salha (2024) attribute the user-friendly and engaging interface of *TikTok* to its advanced features that include facial filters, text overlay, and voice syncing. These visual and multimodal elements support *TikTok* as an effective tool for creating, editing, and sharing short videos (EduTok) that are rich, engaging, and effective in enhancing the educational experiences of students.

In today's tech-centric educational landscape, the compatibility of nano-learning with digital tools like smartphones and social media platforms such as *TikTok* allows educators to transform the traditional delivery of content into a more suitable and engaging delivery that caters to the needs of a new generation of learners (FEU Educational Innovation and Technology Hub, 2023). Furthermore, the simplification of complex subjects into digestible chunks allows learning to be more engaging and less overwhelming for students. This significantly highlights the ability of nano-learning and *TikTok* to transform information into engaging and interactive educational content. Thus, "as education continues to evolve, nano-learning stands as a promising avenue for enhancing learning experiences and outcomes in the 21st century" (*ibid*).

However, there is still limited research on the content, principles, and features of nano-learning, particularly on social media platforms like *TikTok*, and its impact on student engagement and language learning outcomes. Additionally, the effective integration of nano-learning into contextualized language education remains underexplored. These gaps highlight the need to investigate *TikTok* as a nano-learning platform and to develop best practices for creating effective, language-focused content tailored to its format.

3. Method

3.1. Design

The paper employed a qualitative approach to investigate the capacity of *TikTok* videos to teach and learn English grammar. By utilizing this approach, the study analyzed the videos based on nano-learning characteristics and their grammar-related content.

3.2. Materials

The video data were collected manually from the *TikTok* account of the chosen content creator, @the_englishera. She is an English as a Foreign Language and English as a Second Language mentor, IELTS (International English Language Testing System) coach, certified TESOL (Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages) instructor, and digital content creator on *TikTok*, with 526,300 followers and over 2.1 million likes as of November 2024. She has been teaching English online and in-person for over nine years, specializing in both EFL and ESL. In addition to sharing grammar-focused videos on *TikTok*, @the_englishera runs an online English-Speaking Program. Her content often highlights the cultural and linguistic nuances of Filipino speakers of English. She was chosen as the focus of the study because her style of explanation and the examples she uses are relatable to Filipino users. However, it is also notable that her following extends beyond the Filipino demographic. Observing the

commenters in her videos reveals that people from other nationalities often ask questions related to her content. This makes her more influential as a content creator, as she bridges cultural and linguistic gaps, appealing to a diverse audience. This also highlights the universal relevance and accessibility of her explanations, further amplifying her impact on a global scale. This cross-cultural engagement positions her as a unique resource for individuals seeking grammar-related knowledge, regardless of their background.

The researchers collected fifty-five ($N = 55$) videos from the Grammar tab of @the_englishera. The videos were posted between December 6, 2021, and September 9, 2024. The materials consisted of short-form videos highlighting specific grammar rules. Most of the videos feature the content creator herself, accompanied by dynamic visuals and clear text overlays.

3.3. Procedure

The study was conducted using qualitative content analysis (QCA). This approach is focused on analyzing and interpreting non-numerical data. This is accomplished by determining the themes, patterns, and meaning in the material.

Mayring (2014), cited in Selvi (2019), referred to QCA as “a powerful analytical method used for the subjective interpretation of the contents of qualitative data in a systematic and context-dependent manner” (p. 440). Using this analysis, the researchers were able to: (a) break down the data into workable units; (b) identify salient themes and subthemes associated with the content and characteristics of nano-learning; and (c) derive insights from this context-specific analysis.

This approach allowed for better insight into the way the materials were structured, as well the meaning and goals intended in the videos, yet accommodated the nuances intrinsic to the data. For this analysis, it was essential to consider how short-form, bite-sized videos found on *TikTok* can align with nano-learning principles, which include information that is concise and easy to digest.

4. Results

We first opted for unpacking language learning topics and competencies in EduTok videos. ‘Identifying and categorizing topics’ was essential for conducting this qualitative analysis, as it provides an overview of how the nano-lessons are structured. This approach also offers insights into whether the learning competencies are manageable and can be effectively packaged into bite-sized content without compromising content quality.

Table 1
Topic Categories of EduTok Videos

Major Categories	Frequency
Verbs and Tenses	16
Prepositions	13
Sentence Structure	11
Grammar Mistakes and Errors	6
Articles and Quantifiers	5
Adjectives and Comparisons	4
Total	55

The first category, which appears most frequently, addresses the correct use of various verb forms, including the distinction between tenses, modals, and auxiliary verbs. The second category focuses on the proper use of prepositions to accurately express time, location, and specific contexts. The sentence structure category includes the correct application of punctuation, verb tense, subject-verb agreement, and other grammatical elements when constructing sentences. The grammar errors category emphasizes improving accuracy by avoiding common mistakes, using contractions correctly, and distinguishing between similar expressions. The articles and quantifiers section covers the proper use of articles and quantifiers to indicate quantity or specificity in relation to countable and uncountable nouns. The final category focuses on understanding and applying different forms of adjectives in various contexts, as well as recognizing alternative expressions.

The first three categories clearly account for over 70% of the total topic frequency. Since verb conjugation and tense usage can be difficult due to the complexity of multiple verb forms (Allard & Mizoguchi, 2021), irregular verbs, and the nuanced use of tenses to convey context and time, they are frequently revisited in grammar lessons. Similarly, learners often struggle with the correct use of prepositions (Sanjaya & Bram, 2020), which is why this topic is emphasized in grammar classes to help students understand the specific relationships between objects, locations, and time in English. Both areas are closely related to sentence structure, as English has a distinct structure, particularly regarding word order and the use of sentential elements. This may explain why many users who comment on the content creator's videos frequently request further elaboration on these topics. The topics influence the planning, creation, and posting of the content.

In addition to topics, grammar competencies must also be categorized, as they represent broader learning goals and outcomes that learners are expected to achieve through engagement with the topics. These competencies extend

beyond mere knowledge acquisition to encompass skills, thereby enabling targeted instructional strategies. The grammar competencies are classified into four areas: (a) competencies on verb forms and tense usage, (b) competencies on understanding the correct usage of prepositions, (c) competencies on correct use of pronouns and quantifiers, and (d) competencies on error awareness and self-correction.

The EduTok videos cover a wide range of grammar competencies about differentiation and application of verb forms and tenses. These include mastering subtle grammatical differences, including ‘made of’ and ‘made from’, or even using the subjunctive forms like ‘if I were like you’ instead of using the indicative form ‘if I was you’. The videos further show the use of tense markers, including ‘have’, ‘had’, and ‘have had’, in addition to using prepositions—such as ‘in’, ‘on’, and ‘at’—with verbs towards greater grammatical accuracy. Beyond basic differences, the videos also showcase mastery of verb formations, such as ‘used to’, ‘be used to’, and ‘get used to’, as well as auxiliary words like ‘should have’ and ‘shouldn’t have’, which are used to express regret or past hypotheticals. Being able to use modal verbs like ‘could’, ‘would’, and ‘should’ proficiently is indicative of one’s ability to convey subtle meaning that is attached to modality and context. The findings reveal that the videos do go beyond the act of teaching isolated grammar rules: they prompt and engage the learner to apply contextual and practical skills in many instances when expressing time, preference, and obligation.

The nano-videos also pay strong attention to the accurate use of prepositions related to time and place. Such differences include the capacity to discern between prepositions such as ‘in’, ‘on’, and ‘at’, as applied in context, making sure to consider differences between, for example, ‘in the morning’ versus ‘on the weekend’ or ‘at 5:00 PM’. Another relevant use of prepositions like ‘for’ (to show a length of time) and ‘since’ (to mark a beginning) is to denote temporal connections. Further, the videos contextualize prepositions within more general grammatical contexts, such as in the following contrast: ‘in the water’ versus ‘on the water’. Rather than isolating prepositions as single vocabulary words, the videos show them as part of the way to build both grammatically correct and contextually meaningful sentences.

The *TikTok* videos have shown a range of grammar competencies related to pronouns and quantifiers, including the ability to distinguish subject from object pronouns as in ‘I’ and ‘me’ and how they are used appropriately in a sentence. They also tackled the correct application of singular indefinite pronouns such as ‘everybody’ and ‘everyone’, citing that subject-verb agreement was essential because they are to be used with singular verbs. Lastly, the videos contained examples of quantifiers, both for countable and uncountable nouns. The content also emphasizes the proper use of ‘some’ and

'any' in making questions and negative sentences and clarifies the use of 'other' and 'another.' It also differentiates between 'myself' (a reflexive pronoun) and 'by myself' (a prepositional phrase indicating isolation); this demonstrates how each changes sentence meaning. These skills provide a good foundation for learners to improve their syntactic and semantic accuracy.

The short-form educational contents surveyed exemplify key competencies about error awareness and self-correction. The contents focus more on the recognition and rectification of the most frequently committed errors concerning verb form, preposition, and subject-verb agreement. The awareness would help prevent confusion in constructing sentences. Thus, both accuracy and fluency improve. Videos also exist that focus entirely on how to correct a mistake using verb tenses, modals, and auxiliary verbs, mastering subtlety in grammar. Self-correction is part of this as well; viewers can really understand the spotting and the fixing of errors as they happen. This competency is further bolstered by the focus on contextual understanding, as this guides learners to distinguish phrases such as 'what is he like' and 'what does he like' and ensures that they grasp the nuances of language usage in different situations.

We also focused on key observations and insights drawn from EduTok videos. single grammatical concepts were first tackled. Our analysis revealed that the surveyed EduTok videos focused on explaining single grammatical concepts such as subject-verb-agreement, verb tense usage, prepositions, quantifiers, articles, adjectives, and sentence structure. As posited by Yousef (2023), nano-learning is an approach that focuses on a single concept. This approach presented in the surveyed EduTok videos simplifies learning by allowing learners to digest information without being overwhelmed by the content. While this approach is effective in presenting brief and straightforward grammatical concepts, this can limit the depth of explanation and comprehensiveness of the concept. For instance, one video on error awareness discussed the sentence, '*I have a dozen of eggs', as a common grammar mistake and that the correct expression should be 'I have a dozen eggs.' However, the video did not offer any explanation or grammatical basis for the concept presented since it was solely focused on the idea that the phrase, '*a dozen of eggs', is grammatically incorrect, nor did it provide the grammatical rule supporting this correction. Such observations were also noted in another video on error awareness which presented the sentence, '*It's 8:00 am in the morning', as a grammatically incorrect sentence.

Although focusing on a single grammatical concept is a targeted approach that enhances the clarity of content and allows learners to master one rule at a time, the EduTok videos lack sufficient examples or exercises for reinforcement which is crucial for mastering grammar rules. This was particularly evident in

most of the videos where only three examples were provided to demonstrate the application of the grammar concept. Although some videos utilized binary examples and fill-in-the-blank exercises, these were still limited to only three examples or exercises. As such, the reduced examples and exercises may limit the learners' opportunities to practice and internalize concepts and may highlight the need for supplementary materials.

Another relevant observation from the surveyed EduTok videos is the demonstration of how grammar concepts apply in real-life, relatable communication scenarios—that is, the application of grammatical rules in real-world and everyday discourse. From the videos surveyed, it was evident that scenarios and role-plays were utilized to demonstrate the functional and practical application of grammar rules in real-world situations and everyday discourse. It was concluded by Crovitz and Devereaux (2016) that the placement of a grammar concept in real situations reveals its immediate utility about influencing others, shaping events, achieving a specific purpose, and getting things done with words. Some real-world and everyday discourse scenarios featured in the videos were telephone conversations, meeting with friends, talking to co-workers, and classroom discussions. As mentioned by Turupova (2024), using authentic texts, dialogues, role plays, and real-life situations to teach grammar makes learning enjoyable and interactive.

This application of grammar concepts to real-world scenarios can foster a metalinguistic understanding of grammar, including its rules and functions. For example, one video introduced the concept of subject-verb-agreement by role-playing a telephone conversation between two friends. The sentence, '*One of my friends are going abroad', was identified as a common grammar mistake in subject-verb-agreement and was followed by the discussion of one grammar rule that learners can apply to avoid this mistake. This particular video demonstrated how learners can recognize grammar errors and provided an opportunity for them to understand why it is incorrect and how learners could practice self-correction based on specific grammar rules. Thus, linking grammar rules to real-world and everyday discourse helps learners move beyond the theoretical understanding of grammatical concepts. This makes EduTok videos more relevant and engaging as it makes the content relatable and functional, demonstrating how learners can apply concepts in daily communication.

Common grammatical errors were also addressed in EduTok videos. Making errors is part of any learning process. A significant portion of the surveyed EduTok videos features common grammatical errors in adverbs, countable and uncountable nouns, and subject-verb agreement. Learners significantly benefit from making themselves aware of the common grammatical mistakes, as this error awareness helps learners avoid habitual grammatical errors and allows

them to practice self-correction. In one particular video, words such as 'informations', 'breads', 'moneys', 'furnitures', and 'works' were identified as grammatical errors since they are classified as uncountable nouns. The video further explained that to self-correct these errors, one might want to use phrases such as 'bit of', 'piece of', and 'item of' to count these words.

While common grammatical errors and self-correction were observed as content focus in some of the EduTok videos, they were spread out across the 55 videos surveyed. Categorizing these common errors may allow learners to be more intentional in choosing videos that are focused on common grammar errors. Additionally, discussing potential reasons why these errors occur and highlighting self-correction patterns may provide learners with a better grasp and clarity of common grammar errors and self-correction.

Also, one of the most significant observations of the surveyed videos was the contextualized explanations and examples of grammar concepts. Grammar lessons on prepositions, verbs, verb tenses, and subject-verb-agreement were embedded in relatable contexts and situational examples. As emphasized by Aziz and Dewi (2019), context gives meaning to content. One such scenario featured in the video is the use of the prepositions 'on' and 'at' when buying things online. Another example is how the proper use of the verbs 'have' and 'have had' was demonstrated by giving contextual examples of time expressions. The verb 'have' is used when talking about something that is happening 'now' or in the 'present' as in the sentence, 'I have a headache'. The verb phrase 'have had' is used when talking about something that has been happening all day, recently, or for a prolonged period of time, as in the sentence, 'I have had a headache'. This contextual approach in teaching grammar lessons allows learners to grasp grammatical concepts and relate them to real-world situations. Apart from being a learner-centered approach, the contextual application of grammar concepts enhances the relevance and practicality of grammar instruction.

We also evaluated nano-learning characteristics of the EduTok videos, and noticed (a) brevity and video length, (b) bite-size content, (c) visual elements, (d) engagement and interactivity, and (e) contextualized instruction.

Duration is one of the essential characteristics of integrating nano-learning in learning materials, such as video content. This also sets EduTok videos as a primary source of 'bite-size' and 'specific' content. The videos feature targeted and manageable chunking of information presented in a short amount of time.

As shown in Table 2 (below), the EduTok videos are categorized into four duration segments. Videos lasting 5 to 15 seconds are classified as ultra-concise format, as they typically focus on defining terms, explaining a single, straightforward concept, or providing quick tips. These videos are particularly

effective at capturing viewers' attention and engaging users with very limited attention spans. This format is ideal for a specific audience demographic seeking actionable and immediate takeaways. Core concept delivery works well in 16 to 30-second videos, as they offer slightly more depth compared to ultra-concise formats. This allows for a clearer explanation and demonstration of a single concept. By balancing brevity with comprehension, this approach ensures viewers can grasp the topic while maintaining their engagement.

Table 2
Video Duration of the EduTok Videos

Duration	Frequency
5 to 15 seconds	2
16 to 30 seconds	12
31 to 60 seconds	37
61 seconds and above	4
Total	55

It is evident that the majority of the videos produced fall within the 31 to 60-second range, as the average video length is 39 seconds. These videos are likely categorized as contextualized learning (CL), which offers sufficient time to introduce a concept, provide examples, and briefly contextualize it in a way that is both effective and concise. CL enhances understanding

and retention by connecting concepts to real-life applications, requiring minimal elaboration or quick problem-solving strategies. The final category is dedicated to videos lasting 61 seconds or more, referred to as expanded nano-learning. This format allows for a more comprehensive explanation of moderately complex concepts and topics, incorporating more examples, visuals, and even a brief question-and-answer segment to boost engagement with viewers, despite the absence of real-time interaction. It creates a deeper understanding while maintaining the format's concise and accessible nature, making it ideal for learners seeking slightly more detailed insights.

Packaging information into short, focused content sets is a hallmark of nano-learning, which relates to the brevity of EduTok videos. Samala et al. (2023) mentioned that chunking complex topics into smaller components promotes better retention and engagement among learners. In this study, the integration of nano-learning focuses on prioritizing one specific grammar topic or concept in each episode posted by the content creator. Setting targeted language learning objectives per video helps the viewer improve focus and avoid cognitive overload. The scalable and incremental discussion of parts of speech—such as verbs and tenses, pronouns, and prepositions—along with sentence writing, error awareness, and self-correction, encourages learners to gradually take responsibility for their learning through scaffolded progression.

Integrating visual elements into the videos effectively creates connections and relevance to other learning skills by unlocking competencies that require comprehension beyond text. Since the videos are posted on a popular social media platform that allows multimodal content creation, combining

elements—such as videos, pictures, superimposed texts, animations, and other graphics that catch viewers' attention—is highly effective in reinforcing and channeling skills for long-term use. The synchronized text and word capitalization present in all of the content creator's videos ensure that learners can immediately relate visual information to the spoken content, helping them grasp concepts more effectively. This approach is highly beneficial in fast-paced environments, such as *TikTok*. In addition to seamlessly integrating text with spoken content, the educational value of the videos is enhanced by emphasizing text through color changes, placing text cards over key words, and incorporating contextual visuals (e.g., images of the words described). Another example is the use of a timeline to illustrate the time element when choosing the correct verb in a sentence.

Engaging and interactive elements in EduTok videos promote meaningful learning by encouraging active viewer participation. As Radzitskaya and Islamov (2024) note, these features can be used to create educational challenges, check knowledge, or pose problems for independent solutions. This approach emphasizes the significance of limited and focused learning, which, although it demands concentrated effort, may be more efficient in terms of content delivery and comprehension.

In the EduTok videos, the content creator often uses movements to provide better visualization of the topic (e.g., she incorporated body actions to indicate prepositions). She is also using skits to deliver sentences (e.g., question-and-answer formats, situations, and scenes set in classrooms, streets, parks, and home). These make the videos more engaging since most of the posted content on *TikTok* uses similar techniques to attract viewers and enhance user-engagement. This is critical in ensuring novelty in the delivery without compromising knowledge transfer and retention. To guarantee additional engagement, some videos end with a question to the audience for them to answer in the comment sections; some videos use fill-in-the-blank strategy and binary choice exercises, as micro-assessment. She normally responds to the answers posted as comments by the viewers and provides feedback on whether their answers are correct or need corrections.

These practices promote learner autonomy by encouraging viewers to take ownership of their learning. The goal of this strategy is to empower learners in practicing and applying their learned linguistic knowledge independently. This also trains them to use their skills in other communicative practices that might come with complex situations. Additionally, when small amounts of information are easily processed, it also minimizes the cognitive load on viewers and avoids information overload (Radzitskaya & Islamov, 2024). This simplified flow of information does not only help in better understanding but also ensures improved retention as it lets viewers concentrate on the

important aspects without being burdened or overwhelmed by them. By aligning with the principles of cognitive load theory, such as segmenting and signaling, content developers can make their content more accessible and engaging (Albus et al., 2021). Moreover, short content aligns well with the preferences of digital learners who favor short, easy-to-consume formats.

Adding another level of assessment, most of the videos surveyed do not have an animated background, but there are also episodes where she uses contextualized background such as a classroom or an outside setting. These make the videos more relatable and immersive for viewers. These settings can enhance the connection between the content and the learners, creating a sense of familiarity and relevance. This contextualization helps keep the viewers' interest and motivates active engagement by making the learning environment visually appealing and similar to real-life scenarios. Having no background in episodes gives the impression of simplicity so that the learner's attention goes entirely to the content that is being delivered. This, in turn, reduces distraction and ensures that nano-learning delivers the right amount of straightforward information, making it easier for the viewers to interact with the material. Together, these strategies balance visual engagement and cognitive focus to accommodate different preferences and learning contexts.

Creating nano-learning-based videos requires specific instructional strategies that are suitable for certain situations, particularly on platforms such as *TikTok*. This demonstrates how online platforms can facilitate unique patterns of knowledge constructions (Nguyen & Diederich, 2023). Such observations are evident in the EduTok videos of @the_englishera. Aside from role-playing used as a strategy to contextualize information delivery, as mentioned earlier, she also uses a pause-and-explain method. At each critical point in her instruction, she pauses briefly to explain with appropriate detail, allowing viewers to master and understand the concepts prior to moving on. This balances concise presentation of information with moments of clarity, as seen in how she applies these strategies in sharing grammar-related tips by showing phrases that differ in terms of usage from one another and providing additional explanations below the original sentences (i.e., the intention is to use the pause feature of the video platform to allow viewers to read added sentences intentionally). One good observation about how she contextualizes her instruction is that she typically introduces the similarities of the terms first and then gradually explains their differences.

Extending conversational approaches, including giving tips on improving grammar in simple yet understandable ways and providing practice in using grammar rules in everyday question-and-answer exchanges, can significantly enhance language learning. They not only reinforce the concept but also help learners gain the confidence to use the language in real-world situations. For

instance, providing them with tips on common grammar mistakes—such as subject-verb agreement or the right usage of tenses—matched up with examples that correspond with their everyday experiences could make the learning process practically interesting and relevant. The way the videos frame the discussions into a question form establishes a sense that viewers need to achieve something.

5. Discussion

Technology integration in formal and informal education has emerged as a global trend, revolutionizing the way teaching and learning take place across various contexts. With the rise of online platforms, especially during the pandemic, new educational opportunities have also appeared. EduTok has become a leading example of how short-form videos can be used to democratize learning. The educational value of the study lies in using EduTok videos to understand the ways media and technology are incorporated with accessibility and innovation in creating new language learning paradigms to changing learning needs.

This analysis shows that some grammar topics and competencies dominate the EduTok content. Verb forms and tenses, prepositions, and sentence structure are among the most frequent foci and account for more than 70% of the content. The focus on these areas reflects their complexity and the difficulty learners face in mastering them, especially when dealing with verb conjugation, the use of tense, and prepositional phrases. These topics are fundamental for building language skills, especially in constructing accurate and meaningful sentences in English (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2023). The EduTok videos focus on the essential grammar areas, but the concentration on verb forms and tenses might overemphasize this complex aspect of language learning, which could overshadow other important competencies.

Mastering tenses is no doubt crucial, but repeated emphasis on the topic does not necessarily tackle the larger scope of grammar problems learners are bound to encounter. Likewise, though prepositions and sentence structure are rightly given emphasis on their importance in building grammatically correct and meaningful sentences, the material lacks adequate balance among topics such as articles, quantifiers, and adjectives, which receive fewer video uploads. Furthermore, error awareness and self-correction are important skills (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2018); however, they have a relatively limited presence in the grammar-related content. The EduTok videos, although very informative in these short formats, narrow their scope to specific grammar areas; hence they might not present the whole picture of mastering a language. This situation may stem from the issues and needs found by the content creator, which probably affect the planning of the content she uploads. The content

creator seems to adjust the videos according to the questions viewed in the comment section. If this is the case, it could be beneficial for the need-based planning of the nano-learning videos produced by @the_englishera (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2020—on needs analysis).

Additionally, the EduTok videos seem to prioritize simplified, digestible content over accuracy and comprehensive content. This means that although the single grammatical concept approach is a hallmark feature of nano-learning, the oversimplification of complex grammatical concepts, such as verb tenses and subject-verb-agreement, in EduTok videos may potentially lead to fragmented learning experiences, misconceptions, and overgeneralization of grammar rules. The reduced examples and exercises that can be attributed to the single-concept nature of EduTok videos is also limiting in terms of opportunities to practice, internalize, and apply grammatical concepts. Likewise, since EduTok videos are brief and straightforward, discussions focused on common grammar errors tend to simply focus on the identification of the error without explaining much or offering grammatical basis to support the correction. Consequently, learners may be encouraged to access supplementary resources or materials with expanded, more comprehensive content.

Nevertheless, contextual approach and the application of grammatical rules in everyday real-world discourse supplement the isolated and simplified nature of EduTok videos. This balanced approach not only boosts the level of understanding but also connects theory with practical application. The utilization of role-plays, dialogues, and other real-life relatable communication scenarios demonstrate the functional and practical application of grammar concepts in daily communication. While there are significant limitations on examples and exercises in these videos, learners are given the opportunity to observe and familiarize themselves with relatable application of grammar rules. The contextual application of grammar concepts—such as when talking over the telephone, conversations with co-workers, and classroom discussions—features in some of the videos and enhances the relevance and practicality of grammar instruction.

While brevity is one of the salient features of nano-learning, emphasis on extremely short videos might result in reduced depth and complexity of content. For example, in the ultra-concise format, only basic information and quick tips are possible in 5-15 seconds, which might not be enough for the viewer who wants to know a more in-depth explanation of more complex examples. This format may be particularly useful for presenting basic concepts and risks oversimplifying to the point where it leads to shallow learning. Complex grammatical rules, for example, may not be practically addressed in

such short duration videos, potentially leaving viewers with incomplete or misinterpreted understandings.

The videos feature interactive elements like quizzes, challenges, and audience feedback. However, the level of engagement remains largely passive. With elements of call-to-action in place, the *TikTok* format does not lend itself well to deep interaction. The absence of real-time feedback or interaction with learners may reduce the depth of engagement as responses to questions are often delayed and may not provide immediate corrective guidance when needed, which may affect the learning process. EduTok videos are quite efficient in delivering quick, easy-to-access learning but face significant challenges with depth and sustainability. A more thoughtful and consistent application of contextualization strategies would enhance the educational value of the videos, especially when catering to certain linguistic demographics, such as Filipinos learning English, as most of her commenters are from the Philippines or use the Filipino language when interacting with her.

6. Conclusion

This study analyzed EduTok videos as an emerging nano-learning resource, especially for short and easily digestible content on teaching and learning grammar in the English language. The analyses reflected the inherent challenges of viewers mastering the nature of verb conjugations, tense usage, and prepositional contexts. This categorization of topics and competencies shows that, aside from presenting isolated grammar rules, the videos contextualize the application of the same rules. While this foundation is critical for the development of proficiency in a language, the potential drawback could be the downplaying of other equally significant areas, such as sentence construction in advanced sentences or vocabulary building. Such short-form videos provide opportunities for the development of grammatical accuracy, error awareness, and self-correction among learners in a very brief, engaging format.

The self-contained, small, and unified approach of nano-learning observed in EduTok videos allows for a straightforward and simplified delivery of content that does not overload learners. While this nature of EduTok videos is a hallmark of nano-learning, challenges on the simplification of complex content and the reduced explanation and examples limit the learners' opportunity to understand grammatical concepts that support the correction of common grammar errors and may lead to the misconceptions and overgeneralization of complex grammar rules. This challenge, however, is supplemented by the contextual and real-life applications of grammar concepts demonstrated through dialogues and role-plays of telephone conversations, conversations with friends or co-workers, and classroom discussions. These applications

offer opportunities for learners to interact with the content and observe how these grammatical concepts can be applied in real-life, everyday discourse.

EduTok videos effectively utilize nano-learning principles by balancing briefness, bite-sized portions, and contextualized instructions to deliver targeted language acquisition. Since most of the videos are between 31 and 60 seconds, they condense teaching grammar in a coherent manner, making it possible for clear explanations, examples, and real-world applications without overwhelming the viewer. Visual elements, such as synchronized text, contextual images, and interactive features like skits and comment-based exercises, enhance engagement and retention, and reinforce the connection between the content and learners' everyday experiences. This would be followed by the usage of role-playing, pause-and-explain techniques, and gradual clarification of grammar rules, thereby enabling learners to not only know the main ideas but also give them confidence to apply those concepts in a practical way. This mix of brevity, visual engagement, and interactive learning will make EduTok an efficient tool for language acquisition and enable the learner to process and retain information in an easily managed, relatable, and engaging format.

Future research could build on these findings by analyzing a larger dataset of *TikTok* videos to evaluate the platform's broader applicability for language learning. Researchers could also conduct experimental and quantitative studies to assess the impact of nano-learning on grammar comprehension, retention, and application. Additionally, further studies might investigate the potential of *TikTok* as a tool for teaching other language skills, such as speaking, listening, and vocabulary acquisition. Exploring these areas would significantly advance the understanding and development of digital language education.

Authors' Statement

The authors discussed and conceived the article together. They both manually collected and analyzed the materials. Further, Mr. Bosque is responsible for the Abstract, Introduction, discussion on Digital Platforms and Language Learning, Research Design, Materials, Procedure, Results 4.1 and 4.3, Discussion, and Conclusion. While Ms. Pagal is responsible for the Abstract, Features of Nano-learning, Materials, Results, Discussion, and Conclusion.

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